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Research Article

**A SHORT-TERM RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE ASSOCIATION
OF METABOLIC DISORDER REGULARITY AMONG BOTH
DIABETIC PATIENTS AND NON-DIABETIC PATIENTS**¹Dr. Nadeem Malik, ²Dr. Unbreen Pervaiz, ³Dr. Sibtain Jahangir¹SMO, Holy Family Hospital, Rwp²WMO THQ Kallar Syedan³IMO, BHU Kot Haq Nawaz**Abstract:**

Objective: To associate regularity of Metabolic Disorder amongst diabetic and non-diabetic out-casualties of tertiary public health care center having enlarged stomach perimeter.

Methods: The short-term research was led in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore (April to October 2017). Overall of 110 sufferers i.e. 55 diabetics patients and 55 nondiabetics patients were carefully chosen by non-probability, purposive sampling method. After enchanting informed agreement, sufferers of age 35-55 years having stomach perimeter >104 cm in males and >90 cm in females non-diabetic patients plus diabetic patients for two years were inducted in this research from out causality subdivision, whereas sufferers with ischemic heart illnesses, nephrotic disorder and gestational diabetes were omitted. Blood model was taken for lipid profile and blood glucose after 14 hours of fasting. Stomach perimeter in traditional vertical situation was calculated. Related evidence together with age, sex, stomach perimeter, fasting blood glucose, lipid levels and analysis of Metabolic Disorder were noted on proforma by a doctor and studied over software version SPSS.

Results: Amongst diabetic patients, 64% were men and 36% were women whereas in non-diabetic's patients, 56% were men and 44% were women. 100% diabetic sufferers had dyslipidemia in comparison with 90% non-diabetic patients. Amongst diabetic patients, 90% were hypertensive where as 36% non-diabetic patients had hypertensive. 38% of diabetic sufferers and 26% of non-diabetic sufferers must metabolic disorder ($p = 0.002$).

Conclusion: There was a meaningfully high quantity of Metabolic Disorder with enlarged stomach perimeter in diabetic sufferers.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Metabolic Disorder, Waist-hip Proportion.

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INTRODUCTION:

The present age has understood the increase of automation and modernization, with enhanced transportation subsequent in variations in life from energetic to inactive and therefore, creation a massive influence on humanoid wellbeing [1]. The growth in Metabolic Disorder has been temperately connected to the accomplishment in community healthiness thru the last century, having individuals existing lengthier due to removal of numerous of the infectious illnesses. Over the last three decades, emphasis on Metabolic Disorder has frequently amplified, identifying this as one of main worldwide community healthiness tasks of current era [2]. Metabolic Disorder is considered by group of medical principles: insulin confrontation, overweightness, hypertension, and atherogenic dyslipidemia [3]. Gerald Reaven in 1990 remained foremost scientist to name the group as per disorder [4]. Metabolic Disorder has been well defined in diverse customs, though, the original worldwide description of metabolic disorder by International Diabetes Federation (IDF) permitted relative international researches [5].

Metabolic Disorder is a main dangerous issue for growth of type-2 diabete patient mellitus and is accountable for epidemics of cardiovascular illness in maximum of the universe [6]. Insulin confrontation is foundation of maximum, if not all of the structures of this disorder. Therefore, hyper insulinemic, glucose intolerance, type-2 DM, hypertriglyceridemia, also little HDL cholesterol attentions might stay accounted for by confrontation to activities of insulin on carbohydrate besides fat breakdown [7]. There are statistics to sustenance the idea that insulin confrontation or its related hyperinsulinemia are sovereign danger issues for cardiovascular illness, this connotation is until now to be established in large scale, potential medical researches [8].

Overweightness is too measured to be a significant issue in aetiology of Metabolic Disorder as it donates to hyperglycemia, hypertension, high serum cholesterol, little high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, insulin confrontation, plus its connotation with developed Cardiovascular Disease (CVD) risk [9]. Numerous researches have revealed that dominant fat accretion is a prognostic feature of the Metabolic Disorder [9]. Adding to this overall overweightness, the spreading of body overweight is autonomously connected having Metabolic Disorder within grownup males plus females, mainly amongst individuals of usual body mass [10]. Due to diverse descriptions, occurrence of the Metabolic Disorder has been stated steadily to range from 15% to 45% in

maximum western and eastern nations [11]. In Epidemiological Study of Urban Karachi, Pakistan, the occurrence of Metabolic Disorder was noted to be 14%, 22%, and 29% using the WHO, Adult Treatment Panel III statement, and IDF descriptions, correspondingly [12]. Approximation of occurrence of Metabolic Disorder is vital for estimate of upcoming consignment of type-2 DM and Cardiovascular Disease (CVD). It is thus vital that these persons having Metabolic Disorder must be recognized and cured as early as possible. The goal of our research is to associate occurrence of Metabolic Disorder amongst diabetic patients and non-diabetic thru enlarged stomach perimeter. We trust that rate of Metabolic Disorder amongst diabetic sufferers having increased stomach circumferences important as associated to non-diabetic sufferers.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The short-term research was led in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore (April to October 2017) with a sample size of 110 sufferers. The sample remained planned by by means of WHO software where level of significance (%) = 5, power of test (%) 2 - _ = 95, test rate of population percentage $P_o = 0.39$. Estimated worth of inhabitant's proportion $P_a = 0.54$. Sample $n = 79$. A sample of 100 sufferers was engaged to avoid risks of type 2 error. The reference research castoff for sample calculation was from Imam SK *et al*. Throughout the research time, a total of 110 sufferers (applicants), having age of 35-55 years, in those 55 were diabetic patients and 55 were non-diabetic patients were chosen by non-probability, purposive sampling method. The diabetic patients with larger than 4 years of treatment and non-diabetic sufferers with stomach perimeter >104 cm in males and > 90 cm in females attend out-patient section of Medical Unit-II were involved. The sufferers with Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD), nephrotic disorder, gestational diabetes and familial hyperlipidemia were omitted. sufferers offering complaints and history was asked. Overall bodily checkup was completed. Blood sample was taken for blood glucose and fat profile after 14 hours of fasting. Stomach perimeter in conventional upright situation was restrained. Blood pressure was also noted. Learnt agreement about these processes was taken from the sufferers. Applicable info together with age, sex, stomach perimeter, fasting blood sugar, fat levels and analysis of Metabolic Disorder was verified by a doctor on a planned pre-tested proforma.

Arithmetical study was done by means of SPSS version22. Rates and proportions were calculated to present the categorical variables like gender, sufferers presenting grievance, dyslipidemia, hypertension and

Metabolic Disorder; chi-square test was done to associate the overhead stated categorical variables amongst diabetic patient and non-diabetic patient sets and Fisher's Exact test was done according to disorder of Pearson's Chi-square test that if was fewer than 6 is accurate, while suitable test of significance. Numeric response variables like age, time of diabetes mellitus, systolic and diastolic blood pressures, fasting and arbitrary blood sugar levels and fat variables were obtainable by Mean $\pm$ SD; Students t-test (unpaired) was done to relate means of those numeric answer variables among diabetic patients and non-diabetic patients sets. Arithmetical significance was completed at $p < 0.06$.

RESULTS:

A whole of 110 sufferers (55 diabetic sufferers plus 55 non-diabetics patients) remained invested in research. Amongst diabetics, 32 (64%) were men and 18 (36%) were women whereas in non-diabetic patients set, 30 (60%) remained males also 20 (40%) remained females. Average age of diabetic sufferers noted 42.7 ± 7.05 years whereas mean age of non-diabetic sufferers was 42.4 ± 7.62 years. Statistically irrelevant alteration of gender circulation ($p=0.684$) and mean age ($p=0.852$) was experiential in both sets. Sufferers of diabetic set had past of diabetes with normal duration of 8.23 ± 4.33 years. Twenty-seven (54%) non-diabetic sufferers and 13 (26%) diabetic patients offered with fever. Cough was stated by 11 (22%) diabetic patients and 18 (36%) non-diabetic sufferers. Joint issues stated by the sufferers through review of giving grievance are noted in Table 1. Amongst diabetic sufferers, all 55 were observed having dyslipidemia and 45 (90%) were hypertensive whereas amongst non-diabetic sufferers, 45 (90%) were found with dyslipidemia and 15(30%) were hypertensive. This fact discloses meaningfully large percentage of dyslipidemia ($p=0.028$) and hypertensive sufferers ($p < 0.002$) in diabetic sufferers set as compared to non-diabetic sufferers set. In total of 55 diabetic sufferers, 32 (64%) were of Metabolic Disorder whereas amongst 55 non-diabetics sufferers, 16 (32%) were of Metabolic

Disorder. Meaningfully high percentage of Metabolic Disorder is exposed by the facts ($p=0.002$), in diabetic sufferers with an augmented stomach perimeter in comparison to non-diabetic sufferers. Contrast of gender among diabetic patients and non-diabetic patient sets in relative with Metabolic Disorder is shown in Table 2. Amongst 55 diabetic patients, 33 (60%) were men sufferers out of them 22 (40%) were of Metabolic Disorder and 12 (37%) were of non-Metabolic Disorder whereas amongst 18 diabetic women, 11 (54.6%) were of Metabolic Disorder while 10 (49.4%) were of non- Metabolic Disorder. Alteration of Metabolic Disorder was not found to be statistically noteworthy among diabetic men and women ($p=0.406$). In the set of 55 non-diabetic sufferers, 28 (56%) were men out of which 12 (38.9%) were of Metabolic Disorder and 19 (63.1%) were of non-Metabolic Disorder whereas amongst 22 non-diabetic women sufferers, only 4 (16.3%) were of Metabolic Disorder while 17 were of non-Metabolic Disorder. Alteration of Metabolic Disorder among non-diabetic men and woman were too not found to be statistically important ($p=0.112$). Contrast of hemodynamic reply, blood sugar level and fat profile amid diabetic patients and non-diabetic patients' sets are known in Table-3. Mean systolic blood pressure was meaningfully advanced in diabetic sufferers as compared to non-diabetic patients set ($p < 0.002$). Normal fasting blood sugar level in diabetic set was 138.8 ± 22.7 mg/dl and of non-diabetic patients set was 90.5 ± 21.6 mg/dl. Alike design of an amplified regular level was found when random blood sugar was taken 2 hours after a usual food. Regular total cholesterol level in diabetic set was 189.0 ± 18.2 mg/dl, which was meaningfully advanced than the regular total cholesterol 167.6 ± 17.2 mg/ dl of non-diabetic set. A comparable design was noted while associating regular triglyceride level, but meaningfully low average HDL level mg/dl was found in diabetic set than non-diabetic set (42.9 ± 9.12 vs. 47.8 ± 7.32 , $p < 0.002$), which discloses a connotation of diabetes mellitus (DM) with dyslipidemia.

Table – I: Contrast of history of awarding grievances among diabetic patients and non-diabetic patients set

Patient's History	Diabetic Patients (55)		Non-diabetic Patients (55)	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Diabetes mellitus	55	100.00	0	0.00
Fever	13	25.00	29	58.00
Cough	11	23.00	20	40.00
Burning	11	23.00	11	22.00
Epigastric pain	5	11.00	3	6.00
Hepatitis C Virus	0	0.00	3	6.00
Abdominal pain	0	0.00	2	4.00
Vertigo	0	0.00	2	4.00
Diarrhea	2	4.00	2	4.00

Table – II: Contrast of gender among diabetic patients set in relative with Metabolic disorder

Diabetic Group	Male		Female		P-Value
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Metabolic disorder	21	66.5	12	53.7	0.406
Non-metabolic disorder	12	33.6	10	46.4	
Total	33	100	22	100	

Table – III: Contrast of gender among non-diabetic patients set in relative with Metabolic disorder

Non-Diabetic Group	Male		Female		P-Value
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Metabolic disorder	12	39.8	5	16.5	0.11
Non-metabolic disorder	19	59.3	19	83.8	
Total	31	100	24	100	

Table – IV: Contrast of hemodynamic reply, blood sugar level and fat profile amongst diabetic patient and non-diabetic patients set

Variables	Diabetic Group (55)		Non-Diabetic Group (55)		P-Value
	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	145.2	18.20	122.3	19.80	0.002
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	84.7	13.30	76.2	14.80	0.005
Fasting blood sugar (mg/dl)	138.8	22.70	90.5	19.40	<0.002
Random blood sugar (mg/dl)	255.6	73.80	140.9	26.00	<0.002
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	189.1	18.20	167.6	15.00	0.016
Triglyceride (mg/dl)	154.4	17.80	146	12.00	0.002
High density lipoprotein (mg/dl)	42.9	7.09	47.8	5.30	<0.002

DISCUSSION:

The occurrence of metabolic disorder is increasing universal. This is somewhat because of significant rise in occurrence of overweightness. For principal discovery of research about Metabolic Disorder, standards for the Metabolic Disorder planned by a WHO workgroup founded on waist-hip ratio >0.92 or body mass index > 32 kg/m² is castoff. In this, 65% of diabetic sufferers were of Metabolic Disorder whereas amongst non-diabetic sufferers, 30% had Metabolic Disorder. This fact shows expressively tall quantity of Metabolic Disorder in diabetic sufferers

with an enlarged stomach perimeter than non-diabetic sufferers (p=0.002). This fact ropes the report assumed in research hypothesis that there is high number of Metabolic Disorder in diabetic sufferers having an enlarged stomach perimeter. Those outcomes are quite alike with results of Elabbassi WN and Ilanne-Parikka P, et al. But conflicting with that of Vanhala MJ. A gender alteration in Metabolic Disorder occurrence rates can be found in most societies and states. In American whites and Taiwan, the Metabolic Disorder was somewhat more predominant in males than in females. which is

acquainted to our results but in American blacks, Mexican Americans, Turkey, China, Kuwait, Japan and Kinmen females had advanced occurrence of Metabolic Disorder than men. The gender differences are perhaps because of alteration in rate of each metabolic disorder constituent amongst males and females.

The medical status of Metabolic disorder is associated to its supposed impression on cardiovascular illness plus death; in a Scandinavian research, the occurrence of CHD, MI, and stroke were nearly threefold sophisticated in topics with Metabolic disorder as compared to it was in these deprived of disorder. Subsequent query stands up: Do we want to call gathering of dangerous aspects a disorder or would we solitary list individual danger aspects? The mixture of overweightness and hypertension or dyslipidemia was the greatest mutual danger aspect mixture in topics with diabetes [12]. Normal total cholesterol level in diabetic patients set was 189.1 ± 20.2 mg/dl, which was meaningfully developed than normal entire cholesterol 167.6 ± 17.2 mg/dl of non-diabetic patients set. A comparable design was detected while associating normal triglyceride level, but knowingly low normal HDL level was found in diabetic patient set than non-diabetic patient set (42.9 ± 9.11 vs. 47.8 ± 7.32 , $p < 0.002$), which discloses a connotation of diabetes with dyslipidemia. The values for dyslipidemia remained extra dependent on occurrence of hypertriglyceridemia as compared to low HDL-cholesterol; that might present a tricky in patients with type-2 DM, in whom elevated triglyceride levels may be secondary to hyperglycemia [13]. Our research revealed significantly high proportion of dyslipidemia in diabetic than non-diabetic set group ($p = 0.028$). The key reason aimed at type of interference used in high-risk topics in this research is that it might stop, or delay start of type-2 DM and difficulties connected to illness. Sufferers having diabetes with or without signs have a bigger occurrence of both macrovascular and microvascular problems at time once diabetes is identified. Numerous individuals have hypertension and an atherogenic serum fat profile.

As stated earlier overweightness is vital in producing Metabolic Disorder, so central approach to this disorder is mass decrease and enlarged physical action. Though, drug cure could be suitable for DM and CVD danger decrease [14]. It is likely to attain main anticipation of type-2 DM with no pharmacologic interference this might be applied in a main health care center. Restriction of this research is that a multivariate examination would have spoken outcome of other influential issues and weightage of

important result of diabetes with enlarged stomach perimeter leading towards Metabolic disorder. This study would support in management policies for perfect glycemic control in attendance of dangerous issues of Metabolic disorder. Additional constraint of the research is that it does not contain individual and nutritional customs of applicants.

CONCLUSION:

This research highpoints a vital part of physical suitability, exercise and routine walking to control stomach perimeter, hyperglycemia and hyperlipidemia. We also conclude from this research that meaningfully high number of sufferers with Metabolic Disorder in diabetic sufferers than non-diabetic sufferers group by an enlarged stomach perimeter supports declaration assumed in research hypothesis as high amount of Metabolic Disorder in diabetic sufferers with an enlarged stomach perimeter.

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